

Supplementary Methods

1. Experimental Setup

All experiments were implemented in Python via the Hydra framework for configuration management. To ensure comparability and reproducibility of the results, consistent core settings were applied across models:

2. Dataset Preprocessing

2.1 Data Exclusion Criteria

Out of the original 7,503 samples, 102 entries were excluded based on difficulty in identifying emotions. These entries included responses such as:

- "no response"
- "cannot think of anything just now"
- "cannot think of any situation"
- "cannot remember"
- "never experienced"
- "never felt the emotion"
- "I have never felt this emotion"
- "none"
- "blank"

2.2 Deduplication

Additional 73 duplicate entries were removed.

2.3 Final Dataset

A total of 7,328 unique samples were used for the analysis.

3. Experimental Parameters

3.1 Common Parameters

- **Reproducibility:** To control for potential stochasticity during the experiments and enhance reproducibility, the global random seed was fixed at 42 (`random_state=42`). This affects any probabilistic steps, such as data sampling or potential random initializations within underlying libraries.
- **Generation Control:** Max tokens were limited to 100 with a low temperature of 0.1 to promote deterministic outputs. A low temperature value (`temperature`) of 0.1 was uniformly applied to encourage more deterministic and consistent responses from the models.

3.2 Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) Settings

For experiments employing the RAG technique, the following parameters were configured:

- **Embedding Model:** The BAAI/bge-m3 model was used to generate embedding vectors for measuring semantic similarity between input texts and examples in the database.
- **Retrieval:** Efficient similarity search was performed using FAISS (Facebook AI Similarity Search) index. For each input text, the top $k=7$ most similar examples were retrieved based on vector similarity.
- **Similarity Threshold:** Only retrieved examples with a similarity score below the threshold of 0.1 (using L2 Euclidean distance) were included in the final prompt provided to the language model. This threshold serves to filter for sufficiently relevant retrieved examples based on semantic similarity.

3.3 Error Handling and Retry Logic

A retry mechanism was implemented to handle potential transient errors during model inference, such as network issues, API timeouts, or Improperly formatted responses (e.g., JSON parsing failures, missing required fields).

- **Maximum Retries:** In case of an error, response generation was retried up to 2 times.
- **Retry Delay:** A delay of 1.0 second was introduced between consecutive retry attempts.

Parameter	Category	Value	Description
Random State	Common Experimental Settings	42	Global random seed for reproducibility
Max Tokens	Common Experimental Settings	100	Maximum number of tokens per output
Temperature	Common Experimental Settings	0.1	Controls randomness - Low temperature for more deterministic outputs
K-examples	RAG Configuration	7	Number of top similar examples retrieved for few-shot prompting
Threshold	RAG Configuration	0.1	Minimum similarity score to include retrieved example
Embedding Model	RAG Configuration	BAAI/bdgc-m3	Used for similarity search
Max retries	Error Handling	2	Maximum number of retries for inference errors
Retry delay	Error Handling	1.0 seconds	Delay between retry attempts

Table1. Summary of experimental configuration parameters (supplementary-parameters)

3.4 Other Parameters

All other parameters not explicitly mentioned in this section utilized the default values defined in the experiment configuration files.

4. Models Evaluated

We leveraged the Ollama framework to deploy and query all open-source LLMs (e.g., Llama 3.1, Qwen 2.5, Mistral, Gemma3) locally, providing a uniform API interface for running each prompt strategy during our experiments. For GPT-4o, we accessed the model through the OpenAI

endpoint API, and for Claude-3.5, the Anthropic endpoint API was used. The complete list of models used in the experiments is provided in Table 2.

Model Name	Model Size	Architecture	Prompt Sensitivity	Type	Availability
Qwen 2.5	1.5B, 7B, 14B	Decoder-only Transformer	High	Open-Source	Yes
Gemma 3	1B, 4B, 12B	Decoder-only Transformer	High	Open-Source	Yes
Mistral	7B	Decoder-only Transformer	High	Open-Source	Yes
Llama 3.1	8B	Decoder-only Transformer	High	Open-Source	Yes
Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Exact size not public	Transformer + RLHF	Low	Commercial	No
GPT-4o	Exact size not public	Transformer + RLHF	Low	Commercial	No

Table 2. The names, model sizes, and specific characteristics of all models utilized in the experiments.

5. Prompt Strategies

1. Instruction:

Provide clear instruction to the model about the primary task.

Example: “Classify the primary emotion in the given text strictly as one of: joy, fear, anger, sadness, disgust, shame, and guilt.”

2. Output:

Specifies how the model should report the results.

Example: “Respond only with a JSON object in this format: {emotion: *one of the specified emotions*, Confidence score: *value between 0 & 1*, explanation: *brief explanation*}”

Afterwards, each prompt strategy component was gradually added (illustrated in Fig. 1a):

- **Persona:** Assigns a professional context to the model.(e.g.,“You are an expert in emotion analysis.”)
- **Definition:** Provide precise emotion definitions to clarify similarities and differences between categories (e.g., “Joy: happiness, pleasure, delight”).
- **Context:** Includes explicit few-shot examples containing text, expected label, confidence score, and brief explanation.
- **RAG examples:** Retrieval-augmented examples selected as the most similar text samples for context-specific few-shot prompting. RAG parameters, including retrieval thresholds and embedding model details, are provided in Supplementary Section 3.2.

Finally, classification accuracy, confidence calibration, and explanation quality on a held-out dataset for each condition were measured.

Strategy:	Description:
No Persona	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instruction + Output ● No examples or definition provided for models. ● Negative-Persona Prompt = instructions are negative
Baseline Persona	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instruction + Persona + Output
Zero-Shot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instruction + Persona + Definition + Output ● No examples provided for models.
Few-shot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instruction + Persona + Definition + Context + Output ● Specific emotion definitions and textual examples help the model to improve the accuracy.
RAG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instruction + Persona + Definition + RAG examples + Output ● Instead of fixed examples find the most similar text samples to provide context-specific few-shot examples.

Table3. The five primary prompt strategies along with their detailed configurations.

6. Prompt Templates

6.1. No Persona

Instructions

Classify the primary emotion **in** the given text strictly **as one of**: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Do not use any other emotions.

##Output Format

Respond **ONLY with** a **JSON** object **in this format**:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

6.2. Personal Baseline

Instructions

You are an expert **in** emotion analysis.

Classify the primary emotion **in** the given text strictly **as one of**: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Do not use any other emotions.

Output Format

Respond **ONLY with** a **JSON** object **in this format**:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

6.3. Zero-Shot

Instructions

You are an expert **in** emotion analysis.

Classify the primary emotion **in** the given text strictly **as one of**: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Do not use any other emotions.

Emotion Definitions:

- joy: happiness, pleasure, delight.
- fear: anxiety, dread regarding danger or uncertainty.
- anger: frustration, rage in response to injustice.
- sadness: sorrow, grief, disappointment.
- disgust: revulsion, strong dislike.
- shame: embarrassment, humiliation.
- guilt: remorse, regret for wrongdoing.

Output Format

Respond **ONLY** with a **JSON** object in this format:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

6.4. Few-Shot

Instructions

You are an expert in emotion analysis.

Classify the primary emotion in the given text strictly as one of: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Do not use any other emotions.

Emotion Definitions:

- joy: happiness, pleasure, delight.
- fear: anxiety, dread regarding danger or uncertainty.
- anger: frustration, rage in response to injustice.
- sadness: sorrow, grief, disappointment.
- disgust: revulsion, strong dislike.

- shame: embarrassment, humiliation.
- guilt: remorse, regret for wrongdoing.

Few-shot Examples for Reference:

```
{ "example_1": { "text": "Getting accepted to university",  
  "expected_output": { "emotion": "joy",  
    "confidence_score": 0.95,  
    "explanation": "The text indicates happiness and excitement." } },  
  "example_2": { "text": "Hearing strange noises at night",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "fear",  
      "confidence_score": 0.90,  
      "explanation": "The text suggests anxiety or dread." } },  
  "example_3": { "text": "Being treated unfairly at work",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "anger",  
      "confidence_score": 0.92,  
      "explanation": "The text shows frustration due to unfair treatment." } },  
  "example_4": { "text": "Losing a close friend",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "sadness",  
      "confidence_score": 0.94,  
      "explanation": "The text indicates grief and loss." } },  
  "example_5": { "text": "Finding spoiled food",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "disgust",  
      "confidence_score": 0.93,  
      "explanation": "The text indicates strong aversion." } },  
  "example_6": { "text": "Making a mistake in public",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "shame",  
      "confidence_score": 0.90,  
      "explanation": "The text reflects embarrassment." } },  
  "example_7": { "text": "Hurting someone's feelings",  
    "expected_output": { "emotion": "guilt",  
      "confidence_score": 0.91,
```

"explanation": "The text suggests remorse." } } }

Use these examples as guidelines when analyzing the text.

Output Format

Respond ONLY with a JSON object in this format:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

6.5. RAG

Instructions

You are an expert in emotion analysis.

Classify the primary emotion in the given text strictly as one of: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Do not use any other emotions.

Emotion Definitions:

- joy: happiness, pleasure, delight.
- fear: anxiety, dread regarding danger or uncertainty.
- anger: frustration, rage in response to injustice.
- sadness: sorrow, grief, disappointment.
- disgust: revulsion, strong dislike.
- shame: embarrassment, humiliation.
- guilt: remorse, regret for wrongdoing.

Retrieved Context:

Consider the following similar texts and their emotion classifications:

{RAG based contexts. E.g.,

Text: during the period of falling in love, each time that we met and especially when we had not met for a long time.

Emotion: joy
Similarity:1.00}

Output Format

Respond **ONLY** with a **JSON** object in this format:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

6.6. Ensemble

Instructions

You are an expert in emotion analysis.

Classify the primary emotion in the given text strictly as one of: 'joy', 'fear', 'anger', 'sadness', 'disgust', 'shame', 'guilt'.

Role

You are an expert synthesizing insights from multiple expert models. Evaluate the following model predictions carefully and integrate them, giving higher weight to predictions with higher confidence scores. Use the detailed guidelines provided below to resolve any ambiguities, especially for the emotions: anger, disgust, shame, and guilt.

<Previous Model Predictions>

1. Model: gpt-4o, {GPT results. E.g., Predicted Emotion: joy, Confidence Score: 0.60, Explanation: The text describes the experience of falling in love and the happiness associated with meeting a loved one after a long time, which aligns with the emotion of joy.}

2. Model: claude-3-5-sonnet-20241022, {Claude results: E.g., Predicted Emotion: joy, Confidence Score: 0.95, Explanation: The text describes moments of romantic encounters and reunions with a loved one, particularly after periods of separation. The context and similar examples strongly indicate feelings of happiness and delight associated with love and reunion, which are classic manifestations of joy.}

</Previous Model Predictions>

Detailed Emotion Definitions and Analysis Guidelines:

- **Joy:** happiness, pleasure, delight.
- **Fear:** anxiety, dread regarding danger or uncertainty.
- **Anger:** An emotion characterized by feelings of frustration or rage, often arising from a perceived injustice or violation of one's rights. Anger involves a drive to address the perceived wrong and is typically focused on external factors rather than personal shortcomings.
- **Sadness:** sorrow, grief, disappointment.
- **Disgust:** A strong, aversive emotion characterized by revulsion or repulsion toward something offensive, unclean, or morally objectionable. It involves an immediate aversive reaction and often includes physical expressions such as wrinkling the nose or turning away.
- **Shame:** A self-conscious emotion arising from a perception of personal inadequacy or failure, often accompanied by a negative evaluation of the self. It is linked to feelings of exposure to social judgment or humiliation.
- **Guilt:** An emotion experienced when recognizing that one's actions have caused harm or violated moral standards, associated with remorse and a desire to make amends.

Pairwise Emotional Comparisons:

1. **Anger vs. Disgust:**

- **Anger** focuses on perceived injustice and involves a drive for corrective action, whereas **Disgust** is about repulsion and an immediate aversive reaction to something offensive or unclean.

2. **Shame vs. Guilt:**

- **Shame** emphasizes a negative evaluation of the self, often feeling inherently flawed, while **Guilt** focuses on remorse over specific actions and a desire to correct or apologize for the wrongdoing.

Additional Synthesis Guidelines:

1. Weight predictions based on confidence scores.

2. Prioritize textual evidence and context from both the input text and previous model explanations.
3. In ambiguous cases, use the pairwise comparisons and detailed definitions above to resolve conflicts.
4. An external binary correctness **indicator** (Is Correct) may be provided as part of the context. This indicator is critical to your decision-making:
 - If the indicator is "No", it suggests that the previous model predictions might be unreliable and should be either discounted or re-evaluated more critically.
 - If the indicator is "Yes", then the previous predictions are likely reliable and should be given higher weight.
5. Integrate this external correctness indicator into your final synthesis process, adjusting the influence of the previous predictions accordingly.

Output Format

Respond **ONLY** with a **JSON** object **in this format**:

```
{ "emotion": "one_of_the_specified_emotions",  
  "confidence_score": value_between_0_and_1,  
  "explanation": "brief_explanation" }
```

1. Supplementary Result

	Model	Prompt	joy	fear	anger	sadness	disgust	shame	guilt	macro avg
			F1	F1	F1	F1	F1	F1	F1	F1
0	GPT-4o	Negative Persona	95.0	84.2	68.3	75.3	71.1	64.5	71.7	75.7
1	GPT-4o	No Persona	95.4	85.5	69.2	75.8	70.5	65.0	72.3	76.2
2	GPT-4o	Zero-shot	95.3	86.1	70.1	75.6	72.8	65.1	73.8	77.0
3	GPT-4o	RAG-BGE-M3	96.1	85.3	71.6	77.4	74.6	67.5	73.5	78.0
8	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Negative Persona	94.7	83.1	69.3	77.0	70.7	64.8	74.5	76.3
9	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	No Persona	95.5	84.6	67.1	75.6	70.5	65.0	74.8	76.2
10	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	Zero-shot	95.3	84.9	67.3	76.4	70.5	62.0	74.7	75.9
11	Claude 3.5 Sonnet	RAG-BGE-M3	96.0	85.6	70.3	78.2	74.0	67.5	75.9	78.2

Supplementary Figure 1. Class-level analysis of emotion classification metrics across eight major models and five prompt strategy conditions.
 (a) Precision, recall, and F1 scores by emotion class. Error bars represent standard errors (SE), and scatter dots indicate performance under different prompt variants.
 (b) Unknown prediction rates by emotion class and prompt strategy.
 (c) Detailed results table comparing final selected models and prompt strategies used for ensembling experiments. Class-wise and macro-F1 scores are reported across six conditions; best scores are highlighted in green, and worst scores in red.